

more than ordinary interest on the physiological aspects of gastro-enterostomy.

He discusses these aspects under two headings, *viz.*, under what conditions does the new opening induce an alteration in the normal course of the food? If the normal course of the food is changed, what are the results of that change? Cannon shows from physiological observations that there is no alteration of peristalsis because of a new opening being made midway in the stomach. The notion that has been expressed by some surgeons that such an opening gives the part of the stomach beyond it rest from activity is quite erroneous. If the pylorus is not obstructed, this continued peristalsis results in forcing food through the normal exit at the pylorus. The physiologist has difficulty in seeing any advantage gained by this operation under these circumstances unless the passage of bile and pancreatic juice into the stomach through the new opening reduces hyperacidity; experienced surgeons now counsel against the operation unless pyloric obstruction is present.

If obstruction is present, food leaves the stomach through the artificial opening, and, though the acid chyme causes a flow of pancreatic juice and bile, it may not receive a proper admixture of these juices. As a consequence a large amount of the fat and the protein of the food may pass out unabsorbed. Chemical examination of the fæces in patients operated on bears out this contention and explains those cases that show emaciation and marasmus following gastro-enterostomy.—(*Boston Med. and Surgn. Journal.*)

THE INDIAN CIVIL VETERINARY DEPARTMENT.

WE are very pleased to notice that the Government of India has sanctioned the publication of a Memoir series in which the investigation work of the Civil Veterinary Department can be dealt with, apart from the annual administration report.

Memoir No. 1 is the first of these publications and contains a statement of the research work of the Imperial Bacteriological Laboratory, Muktesar, for the official year 1908-09 under the editorship of Captain J. D. E. Holmes, M.A., D.Sc., I.V.D.

We wish the new publication a very successful career and, at the same time, offer our heartiest congratulations to the editor on his first number. If anything approaching the high level of this production is maintained, there is not much doubt of the place the Memoirs will occupy in the future of veterinary literature. A special feature is the beauty of the illustrations and plates with which the text is liberally endowed. Neither trouble nor expense has been allowed to stand in the way and the result is an ideal publication.

THE LEGISLATIVE COUNCILS.

WE are glad to see the name of Surgeon-General C. P. Lukis, Director-General of the I. M. S., among those appointed to the newly constituted Imperial Legislative Council. Some of the heads of the Provincial Medical Departments also appear in the lists of the new Provincial Councils, Colonel R. N. Campbell in that of Eastern Bengal and Assam, and Colonel G. F. A. Harris and Lt.-Col. C. Mac-Taggart in that of the United Provinces, Surgeon-General H. W. Stevenson and Major J. Jackson in the Bombay Legislative Council.

Under the former system, appointments of Medical Officers to either Imperial or Provincial Council were few and far between. Sir Alfred Lethbridge was appointed an Additional Member of the Legislative Council of India in 1893, Surgeon-General W. R. Cornish, a Member of the Madras Council in 1883, and Colonel R. D. Murray, a Member of the Council of the United Provinces, four years ago.

SPECIAL ARTICLE.

COUCHERS AND THEIR METHODS.

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WHILST stopping at Somanur in the Coimbatore District, I learnt from the people that the Mahomedan Vydians pay frequent visits to this and neighbouring villages in quest of cases, and that their first appearance was usually in a garden close by the village in which there is good shade and a well. I accordingly instructed the villagers to bring me the quickest possible information about the advent of any of these Vydians.

About two months ago one morning, news was brought to me that a batch of four Vydians had camped in the usual shady spot. I at once repaired to this locality, saw them, held a pretty long conversation with them, but reserved a few further questionings to the evening in the belief that they would stay in the village. However, learning from the villagers who it was that was talking to them for such length of time, they unnecessarily took fright and bolted, and I was somewhat disappointed. Two weeks later a second batch came but as mysteriously disappeared, and a long adventurous walk I took in search of information about their whereabouts proved vain and I returned home quite discomfited. I therefore thought more caution was necessary to get these men at close quarters, and accordingly instructed the villagers not to talk anything to them about me, but that I would introduce myself to them in the course of conversation in a way which could not raise any misgiving in their minds and as after-events

showed, this plan of campaign proved successful.

About five days later another group consisting of five men appeared on the very same spot. I received intelligence of their arrival and immediately I started. I was confronted with one of the batch, a Mahomedan, aged over 50, with long beard and moustaches, wearing a dirty garb and a big turban and carrying a satchel of cloth suspended from his shoulders. With him also came a beggar woman, native of a near village, aged about 70, with a cataract in her right eye who had implored friends to assist her in getting treated by the Mahomedan. The fee arranged for, I understood, to be Rs. 3 in cash and 1 in kind, to meet the cost of supplies to the group. The Vydian presently laid his satchel on a pial and took his seat there. The patient was made to sit in front of the Vydian, the Vydian facing her as the barber faces the man whom he shaves. In this connection I must admit that these Vydians are ambidextrous, using the right hand for the left eye and the left for the right. Their hands are not at all shaky though some of them are over 60 years, everyone of them being a total abstainer from drinking and smoking. They, however, chew tobacco to any extent. The Vydian then took from his satchel a betel-leaf box of Malabar make which on his opening it proved to be his box of surgical instruments as well; for he had promiscuously put into this box not only his betel-leaf, areca-nut, chunam and tobacco which formed his chewing material, but as well a hook, a—what I afterwards recognised to be—lancet, a copper probe and a penknife which formed his surgical equipments and some old tamarind and dirty cotton—the tamarind being used for cleaning the copper probe and the cotton for dressing the eye. The Vydian presently indented for a stone (on which sandalwood is rubbed and sandal paste is prepared, a common furniture in every Hindoo household) and a chombu (brass-vessel) of cold water. He next took out a small drug and rubbed it on the stone pouring some water till there was some tiny quantity of the paste. Then he took from his box a lancet-like instrument. This instrument, made of steel of Malabar make, is two inches long and is practically something like a vaccinating lancet without a handle. Dirty cotton had been wrapped up the whole length of it; it was hidden in the cotton wool except for 2 m.m. of the point. Its real nature was concealed and, to an ordinary unobservant eye, it appeared but a roll of cotton. Preliminary to handling this instrument, he asked the patient to look well towards the nose and marked out gently on the sclerotic coat with the nail of his thumb a spot for the play of his instruments, no local anæsthetic having been used before. The location of this spot for his operation was done in an empirical way, but the dangerous zone was carefully avoided, the spot being about 8 m.m. outwards from the cornea, and about 2 m. m. below the horizontal meridian

of the globe. He then took the lancet wrapped in cotton and, taking some paste he had prepared on the tip of it, told the patient that he was going to apply medicine only. He warned and exhorted her to look well towards her nose and then plunged the lancet and made a puncture in the spot already marked out on the sclerotic. The patient started with sudden pain and the Vydian told her that "the medicine application" was over. Then he took from his box a probe of copper. This instrument is cylindrical in shape and tapers towards one end. It is 4 inches long, the diameter being about 1.5 m.m. at the broad end. Towards one end at 12 m.m. from the tip, it begins to be three-sided and also tapers, but not to a point; it is blunt. A dirty cotton thread had been twisted round it at the point where it assumes the three-sided shape, to mark as it were the stop as in Bowman's stop needle. He inserted this probe into the puncture to about the mark and then holding it by the thumb and the two fingers, gave a circular motion to it, the puncture acting as a pivot or fulcrum. This motion was intended to tear the suspensory ligament right round and then with a gentle downward stroke, the lens was depressed. He then took out the probe. The instantaneous effect worked as magic on the wondering multitude who gathered round and the Vydian lost no opportunity of glorifying himself. The other sound eye of the patient was carefully closed, and the patient was asked to look with the eye operated upon and tell straight on the things which the Vydian showed her. He first touched his beard which the old woman at once named and the colour of it also, and one after another the woman gave out the names as the Mahomedan Vydian pointed out to her—his fingers, nose, ear, turban and the colour of his dress, and finally to crown all, he separated a thread from his garment and held it suspended before her. She at once identified it and its colour too. The spectacle was, indeed, very marvellous to the surrounding multitude and the patient was overjoyed at the moment. Then the Vydian asked for a piece of white cloth which was supplied to him. He drenched it in the water in the chombu and squeezed the water into the eye. Then he made some paste out of some irritant powder, and smeared it on the skin all round the eye (*i.e.*) over the brow, the temple, the cheek-bone. Then he applied his dirty dressing and the work of the day was finished. I requested him to sterilise his hands and instruments before operation, but to no purpose. I must admit that it was my fortune he did not, for he would have attributed the ultimate failure of this case to the adoption of my suggestion.

This group of Vydians was bold enough to stay in the village for two days, and the Vydian dressed the patient the next day, by which time no marked unpleasant symptoms had set in; probably the free use of counter-irritation helped in

postponing the catastrophe. She identified everything as on the operation day, but I could see some muddiness of the pupil which was also contracted; however, I was not allowed to put in any medicine. It was my good luck again. I must thank the Mahomedan for it. The group left the village on the evening of the second day (*i. e.*) the day after the operation. On the morning of the third day the patient came to me and complained of severe incessant pain and frequent shocks and glares in the eye and in the head, that she had no sleep but ached all the previous night and that she could not rest her head in any convenient posture. The patient now became as much dejected as she was overjoyed before, nay, in her agony bewailed herself and cursed the day she entrusted her eye into the hands of the Mahomedan. She threw herself on my care and implored me to relieve her pain and make her as before, *i. e.*, never minding the vision. On examination, I found her suffering from septic irido-cyclitis of very severe type and I treated it on the usual lines. Treatment for one week allayed the pain in the patient, but it was impossible to give her back her lost sight.

I have had plenty of opportunity of coming across these batches of Vydians and of learning direct from them individually and collectively their mode of life and the methods of their operations. Their accounts all tally with one another. I witnessed also some half a dozen more operations at different hands in different places.

The home of the eye-operators who roam over this portion of the Presidency is Kannadiputhur, a village situated on the banks of the Amravati river, in the Udamalpet taluk of the Coimbatore District. They number about 30 families—all Mahomedans. They are also agriculturists. They own small plots of wet land and when the young paddy plants are transplanted, they have practically nothing more to do till the harvest season. They tour abroad in the interim as Vydians, visiting village after village. They have seen all Southern India in their tours. The couching of the lens is their chief art and their fathers have practised it from time immemorial. They are not only couchers but general surgeons as well, operating on buboes, carbuncles, piles, fistulæ, boils, abscesses, etc., etc., with a penknife they showed me (indeed a wonder), but I did not care to know anything of their general surgery. They generally come out in groups of 4 or 5. They get as fee anything from a fowl to Rs. 50 for a case. The total earnings are shared equally by them. A cook boy generally accompanies them in their tours, but he gets only a half share. This cook is to become a coucher later on as time rolls on. They arrive in a village in which they take up their head-quarters. In the morning at about 5 A.M., they disperse in different directions to the near villages, leaving the cook to look after their bags and baggages at the head-quarters and reassemble in the first village at the usual

shady spot between 12 noon and 3 P.M. quite exhausted. Their life is very miserable and I really pity them. They often return empty-handed, but if any of the group brings a fowl, it was a sure sign that an operation was performed, for they administer the blood of the fowl into the eye. The fowl has a four-fold use, as they say.

(1) It serves as a sacrifice to the deity which presides over the sickness;

(2) Its blood is used to mask the human blood which oozes out from the puncture;

(3) Incidentally the fowl's blood clots and blocks up the hole;

(4) Most important of all, it evidently goes to the Vydian's curry-pot.

Now when all reassemble, it would sometimes be 3 P.M. Then they take their cold rice (*i. e.*), remnant of the meal prepared the previous night. They make plates of the leaves of a plant called *calotropis gigantea* on which the rice is served. After the meal they do not rest but take to net weaving, for when they return to their native villages at the harvest season, they fish which is another of their bye-occupations. In their tours they generally halt in a tope close to a well. Only at night do they prepare and eat fresh food which may be either a Sultan's diet to-day or a Fakir's diet to-morrow, for as Lord Macaulay says of the poets of Johnsonian age "they knew luxury, they knew beggary, but they never knew comfort." These poor souls to whose cruel mercy many innocent villagers entrust their precious eyes, after all, sleep on a pial, on which they also take refuge when there is rain. This is their daily round.

Their surgical equipments are preserved in the queer receptacle—the betel-leaf box of Malabar make. Besides the lancet and the copper probe used in the present operation, they also have a pointed bent hook of iron with which, to use their term they tear pterygium which, with the

knife they carry for general surgery, completes their surgical equipments. I was able to secure from them the two instruments they used in the couching operation—lancet and probe. A drawing of them is herewith annexed.

I.—COPPER PROBE.

II.—STEEL LANCET

The details, place, manner

and method of the operation are the same as in the present case. As a rule the Vydians run away at midnight to another centre before the patients feel the melancholy results of their operation. The apparently astonishing immediate effect, and the positive assurances of the operator have in many cases within my knowledge drawn even the educated classes to them. It is therefore no wonder that the uneducated classes have still recourse to these Vydians. But I am glad to note that even in the villages their methods are being discredited and their fame is gradually dying out, for they leave behind in almost every village many cases of abominable pain in the eye and head after operation. Another point worthy of note is the careful way in which the fact of instrumentation is concealed from the patient, who is made to believe all the time that there is only medicine application. While working in the Government Ophthalmic Hospital, Madras, as an assistant under Major R. H. Elliot, I.M.S., and Captain H. Kirkpatrick, I.M.S., I had often seen patients meddled by couchers even swearing that the Mahomedan Vydian only put medicine and used no instrument whatever. I now see the reason for their assertion and these poor simpletons are not to blame. Some of these Vydians even confessed to me that the operation is sometimes performed under cover, *i.e.*, by spreading a cloth over the head of the patient and operator, as is done at the Brahmin thread investing ceremony when the *Guru* initiates the disciple in the mystery of the sacred *gayatri*.

I am extremely pleased with their way of distinguishing mature from immature cataracts. They generally touch only mature cataracts. It is particularly interesting to note that they very carefully avoid cases where pupils, contracted or dilated, do not well react to light. I had once a patient for cataract extraction and had dilated his pupil with atropine a day previously to know the character of the lens and the amount of the dilatation of the pupil. I showed this case to one of the batches, but they declined to take it up on the ground that the pupil did not react to light.

The Vydians further told me that this art of "litting the eye" is practised in this very same way from time immemorial, that there are somewhere some old texts written on palmyra leaves, laying down the method. He quoted the words in Tamil. They mean "removing the lancet after making a puncture, insert the copper probe and, holding it with three fingers, depress the lens with the three-sided edge." They further told me that the Kannadiputhur families have relations living in the districts of Salem, Tanjore, Trichy and Madura, who practise the same method without any variation whatever.

REMARKS BY MAJOR R. H. ELLIOT, I.M.S.,
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This paper presents several features of very great interest, to which I desire to draw attention.

(1) It is, so far as I am aware, the first eye-witness's description of the coucher's operation, written by one who practises the usual Western operation, and who has been trained to observe in an European hospital.

(2) The method of attacking the cataract from behind, observed by Mr. Ekamabram, has never, so far as I know, been described before. We have always believed that Eastern "couching" was performed from in front, and I am still inclined to think that the front method of working is used by some of the S. Indian couchers, as we find wounds in some of the recent cases which indicate that this is the method employed. Moreover, lay observers have described to us the operation as performed from in front.

(3) The avoidance of ciliary region and of the long ciliary arteries in the preliminary incision is probably more than accidental.

(4) The probe-like instrument with its crude cotton stop reminds us of Bowman's stop needle.

(5) With the above instrument the coucher apparently endeavours to tear through the suspensory ligament of the lens; this would appear to be another intimation that he is not as ignorant of anatomy as one might have thought. It is more than possible, however, that though these men act on well-defined anatomical principles, they are not really themselves aware of the anatomical basis of their knowledge, but act empirically on rules handed down to them through many generations.

(6) The ignorance they display of the dangers of sepsis is appalling and explains the large percentage of eyes lost through septic infection after their operations. This percentage is probably over 40 per cent. (*vide* statistics given by myself in a paper on "couching" in this Journal for August 1906).

(7) They would appear to have glimmerings of a diagnostic sense, as shown by their testing the pupil reaction, and yet they sometimes make bad mistakes, for we see couched eyes which bear clear evidence of antecedent glaucoma or optic atrophy.

(8) The use of the fowl's blood to hide the bleeding from the sclerotic wound is ingenious and cunning. It is well worthy of the tradition of native medicine in India.

Reviews.

The Transactions of the Bombay Medical Congress, 1909—By MESSRS. BENNETT COLEMAN & Co., The *Times* Press, Bombay. Edited by W. E. JENNINGS, M.D., D.P.H., Lt.-Col., I.M.S.

WE have already referred more than once in our editorials and elsewhere to the Bombay Medical Congress, and commented on the marked success of the meeting and on the numerous